

MOTIVATION OF INDIGENOUS STUDENTS IN LEARNING FILIPINO: AN INVESTIGATION

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Motivation of Indigenous Students in Learning Filipino: An Investigation

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the motivation of indigenous students in learning Filipino in public schools. There were 10 participants in this study from Francisco Bangoy High School. After the questionnaire was prepared, interviews were conducted and the responses of the participants were analyzed. The design used in the study was quantitative research. In connection with this, data analysis using the Collaizi method and qualitative phenomenological research were employed by the researcher to describe the lived experiences of a person in an event. The participants in the study were selected indigenous students in public schools. Additionally, the result of the study was to find out the motivation of indigenous students in their studies. Conducting further research about the motivation of indigenous students is recommended to ensure their needs are met. And, to identify the obstacles affecting the learning of Filipino by indigenous students. The study recommended that attention should be given to research concerning the motivation of indigenous students to change the public's perception of indigenous students.

Keywords: *indigenous students, motivation, learning Filipino, secondary*

Introduction

Many indigenous students experience difficulties in learning Filipino. They struggle to learn due to a lack of motivation to study and learn in class. Motivation plays an important role in the learning process. According to Shinta (2012), motivation has several functions in student learning, some of which include deciding which tools can be used to intensify and clarify the purpose of learning to identify various obstacles towards stimulating learning and perseverance in learning.

Ye (2021) mentioned that students at lower levels showed the highest levels of motivation and had less intrinsic motivation to learn. Contrary to the common belief that students with high achievement may have less external motivation. Mauliya, Resty, and Umy (2020) explained that a lack of motivation refers to having an insufficient level of interest and enthusiasm in doing work. However, in the study conducted by Dislen (2013), the lack of motivation still forms a serious problem for both teachers and students in language classrooms.

In the Philippines, 10-15% of Filipinos belong to indigenous groups in 65 out of 80 provinces (Cariño, 2012). Most are located on the fringes. Their underdevelopment has been linked to the fact that most do not complete their education. In school, indigenous students also encounter several challenges such as identity recognition (Milne and Wotherspoon, 2020); low participation or interest (Edwards, 2017); lack of self-awareness (Sani and Bin Idris, 2017); prohibition of speaking their native languages (Allemann, 2019); low vocabulary acquisition (Pearce and Flanagan, 2019). These challenges have contributed to the dropout of indigenous students from academic institutions. Students need to find ways to help them overcome these challenges.

According to Esma (2017), a high school student in Digos City often loses interest in participating in a lesson on the Filipino subject because the teaching style used by the teacher is outdated or passive and not suitable for the topic to be studied, which would otherwise attract active motivation from the students.

In my experience teaching Filipino, many indigenous students lack motivation to learn Filipino because they do not have enough self-motivation. They do not appreciate the subject due to insufficient knowledge of the subject. Others struggle to understand terms in Filipino. It is undeniable that the motivation to learn Filipino among students has been lost, perhaps due to difficulties.

It is important to know the things that help stimulate the motivation of indigenous students to learn Filipino so that teachers can determine which teaching methods to use. The influence of a teacher's teaching greatly affects the development of motivation and learning of students. The learning of students depends on the interest or motivation of the students.

The main objective of this study is to determine the motivation of indigenous students to learn Filipino. It is necessary to know the challenges experienced by indigenous students in learning Filipino. In addition, find ways to facilitate the teaching of indigenous education to indigenous students. I hope that this study will contribute to the existing knowledge about indigenous education.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study is to determine the motivation of indigenous students to learn Filipino. In addition, it also aims to cultivate the obstacles to learning Filipino by indigenous students. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the motivations of indigenous students in learning Filipino?
2. How can the motivation of indigenous students to learn Filipino be cultivated?
3. What are the obstacles affecting the learning of Filipino by indigenous students?

Methodology

Research Design

Phenomenology was used in the study to describe and explore the motivation of indigenous students in learning Filipino. Edmund Husserl, who promoted descriptive phenomenology, aimed to discover, explore, and describe the meanings of a phenomenon experienced and analyzed the data using this method (Augusto, 2019). Phenomenological research was also used by the researcher in their study. The purpose of qualitative phenomenological research is to describe a person's lived experience of an event. This relates to the primary objective of phenomenological researchers, which focuses on capturing comprehensive, descriptive shared experiences concerning the problem or event as a lived experience for each study participant.

Participants

The participants in the study were nine indigenous students from a public school in the City Division of Davao. The researcher used criterion sampling. According to Moser and Korstjens (2018), criterion sampling is a commonly applied sampling technique in phenomenological studies, where participants meet predetermined criteria. The most important criterion is the participant's experience of the uncommon phenomenon being studied. The researcher's selection of participants was based on the study's criteria.

Procedure

The researcher follows steps to streamline the study process. The researcher sent a letter to the school administrators involved in the study, which was approved by the dean of Rizal Memorial Colleges. Then, permission is sought from the City Division of Davao to conduct the study in public schools.

The questionnaire is corrected by the research advisor and then, comments are addressed. Afterward, it is sent to the panels to assess the reliability and validity of the questionnaire to be used in conducting interviews and also by expert validators.

As an interviewer, the researcher ensured that all participants were spoken to, did not stray from the topic, and remained unbiased in every response, listening to and accepting all the information provided. The researcher allowed each participant to share using their preferred language, enabling them to fully express themselves. At all times, the researcher was faithful to the promised duties, especially in maintaining the confidentiality of each individual. The researcher reviewed and explained the data without altering it from its original statements. Thus, these activities are helpful as a researcher in advancing the study and understanding the experiences and opinions of the participants.

Data Analysis

The researcher used the seven stages by Lochmiller and Lester (2017) to conduct a qualitative analysis. These stages are suitable for Thematic Analysis, where the researcher aims to make broad statements that describe and reflect the overall understanding of the data in response to the research question.

Related to the previous statement, the following are the processes followed in analyzing the data. In interviewing, there will be face-to-face encounters with participants using validated questions. Moreover, the participants freely shared their experiences on the topic. The researcher provided reminders during the second encounter after the interview with each to discuss the results and ensure that all written direct statements and their meanings in the transcription of the interview truly came from their shared experiences.

The sequence of data analysis steps is as follows. First, preparing and organizing data signifies readiness to use the instrument for the study, such as the questionnaire to be used in interviews and organizing data collected from various sources and participants of the study. Second, transferring data means that the researcher should be careful in transferring data to avoid mistakes. The researcher needs to consider the accuracy of the steps taken. No data should be lost or altered. Third, recognizing data, the researcher needs to identify if the collected data is relevant to the study. It is essential for a researcher to be meticulous to ensure no incorrect data slip through. Fourth, recording data, be careful in documenting data to avoid mistakes. Fifth, categorizing data requires collecting data, avoiding confusion in data placement, and preventing errors. Sixth, transferring from group to category and category to theme, corresponds to categorizing the participants in the research. After categorization, it is easier to identify the theme reflected in the participants' answers. Lastly, clarifying the analysis process means avoiding confusion in the analysis process.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were taken into account by the researcher in conducting the study. The questionnaire used in conducting interviews with participants was thoroughly reviewed. Experts reviewed the questionnaire used to ensure its relevance to the topic studied. Participants in the study were not coerced by the researcher and were free not to participate in the research. Furthermore, the researcher considered that readers receive correct information and not fabricated data, as there are verifiable evidence proofs. According to Atienza, Bernales, and Rovira (1996), there are ethics to follow in research. In research ethics, plagiarism is considered a serious offense. Therefore, the researcher ensured that due acknowledgment was given to the sources of data or information. In short, the information presented is honest and true, and no alterations were made by the researcher.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the responses to the research questions posed. The answers were derived from the rich narratives of the participants in the interview, organized by themes that emerged from the analysis.

Motivation of Indigenous Students in Learning Filipino

The analysis of the participant's responses to the first question: What are the motivations of indigenous students in learning Filipino? is laid out and explained with appropriate literature supporting the identified themes.

Developing Self-Confidence. This theme was formed from the responses of the participants in the study, where it is necessary to develop the self-confidence of the students. In my analysis of the participant's responses, it is boldly stated:

The motivation of an indigenous student in learning Filipino greatly varies depending on their perspective, situation, and what they are accustomed to. Some possible motivations for Indigenous students like me include embracing culture and tradition; as a necessity in education, everyone must understand each other. (K1).

Undeniable Importance of Education in Life

It is undeniable that education is important in a person's life. It serves as a foundation for achieving life goals. Like the indigenous students who disregard the distance they have to travel. Their life experiences serve as motivation to learn Filipino.

Not all indigenous people know how to speak or even pronounce difficult words in Filipino, so my motivation for this study is to learn to use the Filipino language in communicating with other people, especially in the classroom (K2).

Communication is a bridge for us to understand each other. Even if one lacks knowledge of the language used, one strengthens oneself and continues to use the Filipino language in communication. The continued use of language indicates that one is gradually embracing the reality that it must be learned because it shows its importance in human life.

Having an open mind and interacting with others are ways in which my motivation to learn Filipino was developed (K3).

Having positive traits is essential to facilitate everything. Possessing positive traits helps in achieving life goals. Furthermore, seeking others' ideas does not mean a lack of knowledge but rather, it shows interaction with other people.

Understanding the words in Filipino helps indigenous students strengthen their motivation to learn (K4).

Having sufficient knowledge of Filipino motivates me to be educated and further expand the ideas I have learned (K5).

It can be said that learning the Filipino language is a challenge for indigenous students, but it becomes a way to strengthen themselves. This means that motivation in life is necessary for fast learning of various things.

My motivation in learning Filipino is my fellow indigenous people who are proficient in using the Filipino language. I am glad to have the opportunity to learn it and hope to use what I have learned in interacting with people who are knowledgeable in Filipino (K6).

As an indigenous student, my motivation to learn Filipino is my family because I know that the time will come when I will be their voice or guide (K7).

My motivation for studying Filipino is my dream. I believe that learning the Filipino language will be one of the ingredients to achieve them (K8).

How can the motivation of indigenous students be cultivated in learning Filipino?

Having self-confidence is important not to falter in the complexities experienced in life. It serves as a way to overcome life's obstacles. We have life challenges that require courage and self-confidence to overcome.

According to Pajares (2003), satisfaction and self-confidence refer to an individual's perception of his ability to carry out tasks in fulfilling teaching. Self-esteem refers to an individual who believes in his capacity to perform behaviors necessary to achieve specific performance outcomes (Bandura), self-esteem shows confidence in the ability to control one's motivation, behavior, and social environment.

In the study conducted by Alemdağ et al., 2014, Tekke and Yıldız (2020) reported findings similar to the current results indicating that academic predicts internal motivation. Furthermore, based on the results consistent with previous reports showing a positive relationship between motivation and students' levels of hope, it can be said that as students' levels of hope increase, their motivation increases (Pala, 2019; Ulukan, 2020; Yeşiltaş, 2020). Accordingly, as students' levels of hope increase, their internal motivation may increase. Considering that motivation is an aspect of hope, students with higher levels of hope may study better, try different ways to access learning resources, and make more effort.

Learning the Filipino Language for Communication. In my analysis, the theme of learning the Filipino language for communication emerged. It is evident in the participants' answers that the use of the Filipino language in communication is important. They honestly

expressed that:

The motivation for an indigenous student like myself is a significant challenge in learning Filipino because our backgrounds are different, and the support for culture and tradition is crucial, especially for communication and unity, whether indigenous or not (K1).

Indigenous people like me sometimes do not know how to pronounce or speak fluently in Filipino, so I can use it in everyday communication and eventually become proficient in speaking it (K2).

As the saying goes, "constant practice helps to perfect a task." Everything can be learned if we are determined to learn. The culture one grows up in serves as motivation to strengthen oneself in learning.

The effect of motivation on my learning of Filipino has increased my self-confidence (K3).

The effect of motivation on learning Filipino has broadened and I have learned to write (K4).

Motivation has been effective because it has expanded my knowledge of Filipino (K5).

The saying, "No pain, no gain," proves that nothing is impossible for the person who strives. It just shows that one can teach oneself to learn as long as one is open and confident in oneself, everything can be managed.

The motivation mentioned has helped me continue learning. I have seen its positive effects on other indigenous people and I also want to expand my knowledge of Filipino to use it in interacting with others (K6).

My motivation has a great effect; it drives me to strive harder in studying Filipino to avoid discrimination against me and my family due to our different language (K7).

The effect of my motivation in learning Filipino has made me more eager to discover new lessons in Filipino (K8).

There should be a cultivation of appreciation for language. Language serves as a vehicle for communication. It is a bridge for us to bond and understand each other. Therefore, learning Filipino is important because it is used not just within schools but also outside.

This reflects the report by Suprato, Prahani, and Deta (2021) on language becoming a medium in the production of studies and research worldwide. Communication skills are the aspect that refers to the extent of ability to convey a message that provides shared understanding across contexts where communication occurs (Winger, 2017). According to Khan, Khan, Zia-Ul-Islam, and Khan (2017), language is a vehicle to achieve a specific goal and succeed in interpersonal communication. It is also said that communication skills include listening and speaking as well as reading and writing (Nasiri and Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2016).

In this connection, Komba (2015) stated that communication skills are manifested in the communication process where the relationship between many interrelated skills occurs. This includes a whole series of related actions and reactions that may result in the sharing of meaning. According to Sen (2015), communication can be considered a process because it is an activity connected with a series of steps deliberately carried out to achieve a goal. The process that the sender and receiver undertake requires the same attention to the element of successful communication including the sender, message, channel, receiver, and feedback.

In line with this, motivation plays an important role in the learning process. According to Shinta (2012), motivation has several roles in students' learning, some of which are to decide which tools can be used to enhance and clarify the goal of learning, and to identify various obstacles to stimulating learning and perseverance in learning. Several research studies regarding student motivation by Ehrman (1990) and Macaron (2001) have shown a significant relationship between the use of language learning strategies and motivation in language learning. Therefore, to increase students' motivation throughout the learning process, it is important to find suitable methods or modern aids in learning.

Bernard (2010) emphasized that motivation is related to other factors such as the teaching skills of teachers, learning activities, and the classroom itself. These factors better offer an understanding of how motivation relates to the language learning activities of students. In line with the conclusive statements by Bernard (2010), current research emphasizes that success in learning, acquisition, and use of language is dictated by several factors other than motivation. Parts of these aspects of language learning may include the activities involved in the language class, the attitudes and knowledge of teachers in managing the class, and monitoring the levels of student motivation.

Strengthening Culture and Tradition. In my further analysis of the responses, the theme of strengthening culture and tradition emerged. This just indicates that the culture and tradition from which indigenous students originate are important. Strengthening their culture and tradition reinforces their self-identity. The participants stated:

We have gatherings in our place as a tradition we perform (K1). It is our culture to help our fellow tribesmen who are struggling, by providing food (K2).

Each of us comes from a background, but this has not hindered us from succeeding in life. A place or group is recognized through its culture and tradition. Let us look at the responses of the participants in the study.

There are times when my culture becomes a barrier to learning in school because of the language we use (K2).

Especially since I encounter various kinds of cultures (K3).

Thus, I sacrificed not using our language... because it is necessary to use Filipino in school (K4).

Success cannot be achieved without sacrifice. Sacrifice of important things in one's life is inherently part of human existence. This sacrifice aids in navigating new chapters of our lives. However, a person's culture remains, alongside the language we have grown up with. Let us consider the statements of the participants:

This helps to further expand the learning of each student and better understand both new and old teaching methods because it is important for us to understand the delivery of knowledge as it is crucial in the learning process (K5).

Teachers are crucial for indigenous students to expand their learning in the field of education. Teachers must adapt their teaching to the culture and traditions of the students.

Experience helps in cultivating motivation for learning and understanding using the language learned (K6). As a student of Filipino, it is necessary to have a positive outlook on learning it. This motivates me as an indigenous person who is eager to advance my knowledge of the Filipino language so as not to be ignorant of the events in the community (K7).

My experience in interacting with others is useful and helpful (K8).

Strengthening culture and tradition is important because it shows the interconnectedness of everyone. Each indigenous student comes from a different families. Therefore, it is important to value this by discussing their culture and traditions in the field of education. In this way, fair treatment of their origins can be demonstrated.

A study emphasized the issue of cultural sensitivity according to Hammer (2012) in that it describes the ability to shift cultural perspectives and appropriately adapt behavior to cultural differences and similarities. Meanwhile, Sandell and Tupy (2015) described cultural sensitivity in the context of teaching as the ability of teachers to respond to the needs of students from various cultures, while valuing and maintaining the dignity of cultural differences and similarities among individuals, families, and communities.

In the context of teaching, Gay (2010) mentioned that cultural sensitivity is significant in the field of education because it allows for the expansion and growth of teachers' capabilities in the classroom. According to Partelow, Spong, Brown, and Johnson (2017), cultural sensitivity is a way to bring out the higher potential of students from different ethnic groups. As classrooms become more diverse, teaching practices cannot remain the same, thus, educators need to develop a culturally sensitive and aware curriculum in each subject, including the implementation of a more inclusive and equitable teaching approach that closes the gap for minority group students.

Studies by Kumar, Zusho, and Bondie (2018) show that an environment with aspects of cultural sensitivity aims to give teachers the ability to be reflective, understanding, and appreciative of themselves and recognize the cultural differences of their students. In the study conducted by Marks (2011), it was discovered that training is a prerequisite for the use of culturally related practices. Furthermore, the author found that teachers with informal cultural training rely on personal experience and natural inclination to guide their classroom practices. Gies (2010) found that professional development training can positively affect teachers' perspectives on culture; however, guidelines and ineffective programs can create adverse concepts and views on the importance of culture.

Expanding Knowledge in Filipino. From the analysis I conducted, the fourth theme emerged: expanding knowledge in Filipino. This means that language has a significant influence on expanding the knowledge of indigenous students. The responses of the participants were seen as follows:

As a student of Filipino, it is necessary to have a positive outlook on learning it. This will motivate me as an indigenous person who is determined to improve my knowledge of Filipino so as not to be ignorant of the events in the community (K1).

As a student, we should start by reading at a level that focuses on our learning. The challenge in growing our foundation in reading difficult words, and if the problems in the process of teaching and learning Filipino are solved, it would be a great help in understanding and ingraining each lesson in the minds of students (K2).

Others view the act of reading as a punishment. Like a thorn that wraps around the petals of flowers. However, it is undeniable that it is important in life, especially in achieving dreams. Learning Filipino requires a strong fortress. Therefore, developing reading skills is greatly needed to strengthen the foundation of learning the Filipino language. Let's highlight the experiences of the participants in the study that stated:

The experience becomes effective if it is well utilized and we are allowed to learn Filipino (K3).

My experience in interacting with others is useful and helpful (K4).

My experience is effective in shaping my thinking and behavior (K5).

Not everything can be taught in school. Experience is associated with this to better understand the environment. The experience

becomes a way to succeed in life. It serves as a guide and shield in times of crisis. It serves as a light that provides strength to embark on a new tomorrow. The participants bravely shared the following:

This experience strongly urged us indigenous people to learn Filipino to avoid the discrimination we have experienced and continue to experience from others (K6).

Life experience teaches us to step on the right path. It teaches us to be strong in facing life's challenges. We become prepared for the changes brought by time. This motivated a person to rise and learn new knowledge. Like the participants who wish to learn Filipino because of their past experiences. They continue to aim for success to achieve a better life (K7).

It seems that the experiences and perceptions of indigenous students learning Filipino highlight both the challenges and the personal and cultural significance of mastering the language. This mastery isn't just about learning a language but about empowering themselves within their communities and broader society. It's a journey of both personal growth and cultural preservation, enabling them to navigate and contribute to both their indigenous and national identities more effectively. This dual embrace enriches both their personal lives and the cultural tapestry of the nation.

Cultivating the Motivation of Indigenous Students to Learning Filipino

The responses of the participants regarding the second question: How can the motivation of indigenous students to learn Filipino be cultivated? were presented and explained with appropriate literature supporting the identified themes.

Proper Support from Teachers: Students require the right support from teachers to facilitate their learning. The influence of a teacher on student learning is significant. Here are the responses of the participants to the question:

"My teacher supports me especially with difficult words. I am grateful because ma'am is there to help me" (K1).

"For me, the teacher is important because they help students who are struggling" (K2).

"Ma'am guides me in everything I do" (K3).

The mourning of a teacher for their students brings about significant changes in the learning of the students. Students can be likened to a tree that needs nurturing to flourish and grow beautifully. Like a student who needs someone to support them to cultivate the necessary competencies.

"For me, the help and support that ma'am gives me is a big part. I learn to write and read unlike before when I struggled" (K4).

"Ma'am is kind because she patiently teaches me. Even though I struggle, she does not neglect me" (K5).

As the saying goes, "If you plant something, you will harvest something," meaning that if something is sown, something will be gained. Teachers may not be rich in material things, but the knowledge they implant in the minds of students is invaluable.

"My courage is always boosted, always being told 'you won't survive if you don't strive', that's just how it is, ma'am" (K6).

"I see ma'am like a mother because she corrects my mistakes" (K7).

"Ma'am monitors everything I do" (K8).

The proper support of teachers significantly influences students. Students can easily learn their lessons if guided correctly by teachers. In other words, the learning of students rests on the shoulders of teachers. Students rely on them to sharpen their abilities and skills.

The best and most effective learning occurs when students are fully engaged in the lessons and apply what they have learned in real life, as mentioned by Russo and Russo (2019). It is also suggested that a teacher's enjoyment in teaching lessons is linked to the student's joy in learning, appearing to be a positive and exciting experience for both (Russo and Russo, 2019). Moreover, Greene (mentioned in Davis and Winter, 2019) noted that greater interaction and deeper relationships between students and teachers play a significant role in encouraging students to continue and complete the program.

Additionally, a teacher's presence and responsiveness to the needs and interests of students yield positive outcomes, especially in helping students become independent thinkers and problem solvers (Dislen, 2013, as cited in Tadesse, Manathunga, and Gilles, 2020). Meaningful interactions between students and teachers contribute to a high-quality learning experience (Tadesse, Manathunga, and Gilles, 2020).

Understanding Indigenous Cultures. In my analysis, the theme of understanding indigenous cultures emerged. It indicates that understanding the culture of indigenous people is important because it defines their identity. Participants' responses to the following questions highlight this:

"I see in the culture of indigenous people their livelihoods, where they sell vegetables and more" (K1).

"Many of us struggle because we have not received education" (K2).

"Some of us do not have food... no shoes... no sandals" (K3).

Being poor is not a fault. Instead, it becomes a stepping stone in facing new life challenges. Indigenous people remain open-minded about possible changes in their life chapters. There is a vivid hope in the faces of the indigenous that light will dispel the darkness they live in.

"Few of us manage to study... there's just no money... parents don't have jobs" (K4).

"I just really accepted that this is our life" (K5).

While life is difficult, they continue to fight life's challenges. This is how indigenous people can be described, like ants that tirelessly work and save, preparing even when there is no certainty of success, all for the sake of their family.

"We have embraced this culture... we are used to living this way" (K6).

"What's important to us is having food daily. Even just twice a day" (K7).

"We never lose hope in life. In fact, my family serves as my motivation" (K8).

Understanding the culture of indigenous people is crucial to understanding their lives. The culture of indigenous people differs from the culture of those who have lived luxuriously. Moreover, understanding the culture of indigenous people provides awareness that can change how they are viewed.

This was demonstrated in a study by Ebersole, Kanahale-Mossman, and Kawakami (2016), which examined an Ethnicity and Education course.

Eighteen teacher participants enrolled in a Master of Education program. Course instructors examined the teachers' perspectives on culturally responsive teaching. Data collected included a teaching plan, a post-course questionnaire, a focus group interview, and a follow-up questionnaire. The analysis identified three themes: first, creating culturally responsive activities; second, transitioning towards culturally responsive teaching as a perspective; and third, becoming a culturally responsive teacher. This article suggests ways that educator-preparation programs might reconceptualize culture-based courses to deepen teachers' perspectives rather than merely enhancing activities that support culturally responsive teaching and learning.

Addressing Discrimination. Unknown to many, discrimination is rampant within schools, which led to the emergence of the theme of addressing discrimination from the study's participant responses.

Sometimes, I experience discrimination, especially with my speech... I have difficulty speaking Filipino (K1).

I also experience being mocked because sometimes I struggle with the topics... so, I just stay quiet (K2).

There is discrimination happening to indigenous students because of their physical appearance (K3).

We all face challenges in life. We can consider ourselves prisoners due to the trials that come our way. However, behind the darkness we experience, there is light hidden behind the mask. Here are the responses of other participants.

I am grateful because our school is taking steps to address the discrimination problem (K4).

Our teacher also talks to classmates who mock me... Ma'am tells them that what they are doing is wrong (K5).

I pray every day that everything will change (K6).

Every problem has a solution, as the saying goes. No problem is unsolvable as long as you have faith in God. Discrimination is rampant in various schools, but it is gradually being resolved with the help of teachers and school administration.

After class, I go straight home because I'm afraid I might be mocked by classmates (K7).

No, I don't think about stopping my studies, because I also think about what will happen to me, I didn't think about giving up because my family is my inspiration. So, I never thought of giving up (K8).

It is important to focus on the problem of discrimination because many students have stopped going to school. By addressing discrimination, the number of students who have stopped going to school is reduced. Those who experience discrimination will no longer feel fear and their self-confidence will be restored.

Indigenous students continue to experience discrimination from teachers, students, and schools because of their ethnicity. There are more judgmental teachers than caring ones (Victor and Yano, 2018). Discrimination from peers and classmates is also permitted and not reprimanded. Policies of school systems such as wearing uniforms and shoes become an additional burden on the financial capability of most indigenous families. Indigenous students are also labeled as weak due to the difference in language and context learned in the community compared to the context learned and taught in formal schools (Victor and Yano, 2018).

According to Gilani M.R.A. (2012), how school teachers act to challenge racism in schools is an important concern in an immigrant

society like Australia. A 10% response from a self-administered online survey of elementary and secondary government (public) teachers across Sydney, the largest ethnic in Australia, examined the attitudes of classroom teachers towards cultural diversity, multicultural education goals, and strategies to implement anti-racism. The main components of the attitude survey teased out various influences of opinion on multicultural education, diversity, and anti-racism. Classroom teachers are highly supportive of cultural diversity, multicultural education, and strategies to combat racism and discrimination, and these views are nearly invariant across different geographic areas of the city, unlike attitudes within the general community. However, teachers' knowledge about implementing multicultural policy varies and is positively related to the extent of population diversity and socio-economic status of the communities surrounding the schools.

Promotion of Filipino as a Language. Promoting Filipino as a language is important because it serves as an identifier. The Filipino language should be valued because it is our language. Here are the responses of the participants regarding this:

The influence of the environment on learning Filipino is significant. If we only have enough materials to facilitate the teaching and learning process, it will provide opportunities for indigenous people like me to persevere in our studies and expand our knowledge in Filipino (K1).

Having friends at school and frequently socializing with them is one of the weapons to strengthen my interest in learning Filipino. Let them be our inspiration and guide in learning (K2).

It is a huge opportunity for us, the indigenous people, to value the environment because it greatly influences me as a student (K3).

The environment influences the development of my motivation to learn Filipino because I learn to study better (K4).

The environment greatly influences the development of my motivation, especially in interacting with fellow students, who strengthen me daily and have become my support in continuing to learn Filipino (K5).

Having allies in life helps speed up time towards success. As the saying goes, "No man is an island, he needs companions," meaning we need the help of those around us. By interacting with them, we learn to speak Filipino.

Intelligence, hard work, perseverance, and unity among us indigenous people greatly influence us, especially in our community, which has produced a successful indigenous person who completed their education (K6).

The environment influences my motivation to learn Filipino because I hear my first language daily and the beliefs of my indigenous community (K7).

My learning of the Filipino language was accelerated with the help of people around me (K8).

The implication of the people around us in shaping our knowledge and learning of the Filipino language is significant. Promoting the Filipino language helps indigenous students to change how others view them. Using the Filipino language in schools greatly influences indigenous students to understand the Filipino subject.

According to new research results, literacy in the first language has been concluded to be essential as a general language with cognitive knowledge towards academic success (Eslit, 2016). When the language used for learning is not mastered, students do not become proficient in that language, but it becomes a barrier to learning (Benson, 2020).

Learning and teaching a language is not based solely on intellectual ability; it is also based on the attitudes they feel. This also means that learning and teaching a language is recognized as primarily a social and psychological event and not just academic (Tella, Indoshi, and Othuon, 2010).

Challenges Affecting the Learning of Filipino by Indigenous Students

The analysis of responses to the third question: What are the barriers affecting the learning of Filipino by indigenous students? was presented and explained with relevant literature supporting the identified themes.

Lack of Teaching Materials. This theme emerged from the responses of the student participants to the study question. It only indicates that teaching materials are essential for teachers to meet the needs of indigenous students. Let's look at the participants' responses to this issue.

Lack of learning materials available for study, and a lack of teachers knowledgeable in our language to facilitate translation into Filipino of difficult words, simplify learning, and understand what is written and read in Filipino (K1).

The teaching materials of the teacher depend on the learning of indigenous students. The teacher is a vehicle for developing the knowledge of students. On them, the knowledge-thirsty and needy students rely. Look at the following responses from the participants in the study:

Many new languages are fascinating to the youth today, such as Korean, which has led to the deprioritization of the Filipino language among today's youth, severely affecting the use of our national language in student learning (K2).

Lack of equipment, embarrassment to using Filipino, and parental support (K3).

A task cannot be accomplished without the support of those around us. A lack of interest in learning Filipino serves as a barrier to expanding knowledge. Foreign languages are more embraced by the youth than Filipinos. The youth have become accustomed to being fascinated by foreign languages so they won't fall behind the times, thus they keep up with societal changes. They also use this as a passport to join a group because if you do not know the language of foreigners, you will surely be left behind. Look at the next response from the participants in the study:

My studies are affected by trials, the lessons learned are not valued, and there is a lack of guidance or parental support (K4).

Lack of motivation, financial problems, and lack of knowledge on the subject are barriers to learning Filipino (K5).

Motivation strengthens us to face life's challenges. Even if there are obstacles such as lack of guidance, financial problems, and lack of knowledge, these do not prevent us from succeeding. Look at the next response from the participants in the study:

There are indeed people who do not trust and always tell you that you won't learn anything good, but they do not know the huge impact this has on me; learning has no basis, you only get it if you strive and persevere in studying (K6).

I repeat, a major barrier to my learning is being a victim of discrimination, where the desire to study further is lost (K7).

I think that the barrier affecting the learning of Filipino indigenous students is not being prepared for changes in the environment (K8).

I think teaching materials are a bridge in student learning. It is undeniable that planning the creation of teaching materials by teachers is crucial to be suitable for the level of students. The focus on the teacher's teaching materials is essential for achieving student learning.

Koshy (2017) emphasized the need to create teaching materials that are unique to the trends and issues of a specific race, gender, or ethnicity. Teaching strategies should be appropriate to allow students the freedom to critically analyze power relationships in their society.

This finding can also be linked to the lack of a specific educational design for indigenous people due to the lack of necessary resources like materials (Suazo and Montenegro, 2018). Considering the situation of IPs as a marginalized sector, they are likely to be left behind in academia, as shown in the findings of the current study, where most did not receive any academic awards, only participated in one organization, and were not involved in any external activities.

Similar to this, in the study by Suazo and Montenegro (2018), they investigated the readiness of schools regarding the implementation of Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPE). Sadly, their results revealed that the schools were lacking in necessary resources such as materials and adult participation. Moreover, there were no skilled speakers of native languages who could contribute to the teaching and learning process. This fact alone shows that there is much to be done to improve services for the education of indigenous peoples.

Veteran (2021) agreed that the demand for inclusive education requires ensuring that future teachers of indigenous students are fully equipped to handle multicultural classes. Therefore, to identify inputs that could enhance pre-service teacher education, this study was conducted to determine the profile, experience, knowledge, attitudes, and skills of randomly selected teachers of indigenous students in the province of Occidental Mindoro. Data were collected online through a questionnaire that underwent validity and reliability testing. The findings show that the teachers had graduated with a bachelor's degree in Elementary Education and had been teaching in indigenous schools for no more than three years.

Emerging Foreign Languages. It is undeniable that many languages are currently proliferating in our country, with foreign languages becoming more popular among the youth. Look at the following responses from the participants in the study:

This has greatly developed my communication skills, and I also apply what I have learned in school activities that require writing in Filipino (K1).

Through the examples provided by the teachers, my mind is sharpened in the correct use of Filipino words in communication, regardless of the situation faced (K2).

A language is a tool for communication in everyday life. It is used to develop speaking skills and even writing skills. Although students enjoy foreign languages, these still contribute to the development of the students' knowledge. Look at the following responses from the participants in the study:

Strive and study hard to acquire various knowledge that can be used in communication and to keep up with the language of foreigners (K3).

I can expand my mind on language because of the emerging languages of foreigners (K4).

The activities greatly helped in develop my communication using various languages learned (K5).

Proficiency in speaking using various languages learned is an indication of a person's sophistication. A person's education and expertise

are reflected through the use of various languages in communication. Look at the following responses from the participants in the study:

In this way, I will work even harder to read books and watch Filipino series or films to learn the language of foreigners (K6).

Be honest and strong at all times and above all, continue to study to learn (K7).

What I should do to improve my learning is to continue researching, participating with other students, and listening carefully to the teacher (K8).

Knowing how to use various languages is important because we use them in communicating with foreigners. It also gives students the implication of being able to communicate with foreigners. Students will not have difficulty understanding and speaking with them.

Preservation can be compared to a precious stone in valuing and effectively reflecting the various cultures that the youth grew up with (Khosha, 2012). Additionally, the preservation of the native language that children learn at home was valued and believed to elevate their self-confidence in developing other languages, according to a study by Colman (2017).

Financial Issues. The participants' responses highlighted financial issues. Let's look at the responses of the participants based on the following:

We struggle with our studies because our parents are unemployed (K1).

Our parents did not finish school. My father only reached fifth grade while my mother graduated from high school (K2).

It's hard when you're uneducated... you can't get a job (K3).

The financial problems are a barrier for us to learn in school. The unemployment of the parents greatly affects the students' studies.

Sometimes we don't have food, so I skip school (K4).

It's also tiring to walk to school... Sometimes when the river's current is strong, we can't go to school (K5).

But I still strive in my studies for my family. I want to finish my education (K6).

The sun is scorching, and the road is wide that I tread every day just to reach my destination. Unmindful of the sun's heat gradually burning my skin just to quench my thirst for knowledge. This is what indigenous students experience just to be able to study. Not thinking about the dangers lying ahead just to finish their education.

I dream of becoming a teacher one day to help in our area. It's rare for someone to get an education here because of the hardship (K7).

I work hard in my studies so I can help my family in the future. So we have food every day (K8).

Financial issues hinder the dreams of indigenous students. We cannot do and provide for the needs of a person if we are financially constrained. It's undeniable that money runs our lives because if you don't have it, it will be hard to rise.

As stated in their paper, Galindo, Reginio, Liquid, Sancon, and Advincula (2018) believe that financial ability, marginalization, and segregation affect the learning and social development of indigenous students in Occidental Mindoro.

Conclusions

Motivation is a key ingredient for academic success, which includes both internal and external factors that stimulate a person's desire and interest in focusing on work, roles, or subjects, or making an effort to achieve a goal. In learning, students are at the core of the process where learning is adapted to their motivations (Dornyei, 2016). Moreover, motivation is the reason why students decide to do something and whether they will continue it for the benefit of the outcomes in assessing their learning skills (Nevidet, 2018).

The implication of this study suggests that attention should be paid to studying the motivation of indigenous students. This study could change how people view indigenous students. It serves as a path for better acceptance of indigenous students in schools and the society they engage with. Furthermore, it gives indigenous students the chance to have their voices heard. It will lead to a change in other indigenous students to not lose hope in life. They may instill in their minds the importance of education in their lives.

As a researcher and teacher in Filipino, it is necessary to know the motivation in the lives of indigenous students. Understanding the motivations for learning Filipino among indigenous students has significant implications on how and where to start. A teacher needs to attend training to broaden their knowledge of strategies, techniques, and methods of teaching. Such training can help by providing knowledge about the teaching materials to be used that are suitable for the level of indigenous students. Furthermore, developing the professional skills of a teacher also helps to broaden their knowledge about various things. Continuing education at the master's and doctoral levels will strengthen their foundation in the field of teaching.

As a Filipino teacher, being aware of what happens in the lives of students has a significant influence on shaping the knowledge of

indigenous students. A teacher needs to know their students to understand their life situations. Moreover, researching the profiles of students is a good preparation to know where a teacher should start.

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